

A Study on Impact of Brand Loyalty on Consumer Buying Behavior: Among the College Students

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Abstract:- The research paper focuses on the study on impact of brand loyalty on consumer buying behavior among the college students. Customer loyalty can be defined as a person's willingness to interact with and buy from a specific company on an ongoing basis. It is the analytical study focuses on factors that affects the buying decision and contribution of brand loyalty on consumer buying behavior among the college students. It is a self-prepared questionnaire based on the objective. The sample size of this study is 112 respondents among the college students. In that 83 response from female and 29 response is from male was collected. It is a percentage-based study analyses the loyal customers for particular brands, influence of price and quality, factors affecting to buy branded products and students 'contribution on brand loyalty. The research found that brand loyalty has a positive association among the students. Price, quality and brand image will influence most to purchase branded products. This study concludes that impact of brand loyalty on consumer buying behavior.

Keywords:- Brand, Brand Loyalty, Consumer Behavior, Factors of Consumer Behavior, Products, Quality, Price, Purchase, Brand Image, Decision Making.

I. INTRODUCTION

Brand loyalty is a behavior pattern of consumer. Where consumers get committed to particular brands and the same brands are purchased repeatedly over time. Loyal customers will purchase products from their preferred brands without keeping options in mind about convenience and price. In order to attract loyal customers companies, use different Marketing strategies like reward programs, samples and gifts. Brand will play an important role in identifying consumer needs and expectations. A loyal customer's repeated buying behavior leads to manufacture more branded products and also increases profit.

As per the American Marketing Association (AMA), Brand means a "name, term, sign, symbol or design or combination of these, intended to identify the goods and services of one seller from another to differentiate various factors from the competitors.

In this era of globalization Indian customers experiencing more national and international brands with new features and better quality. There are several factors

which influence the consumer decision making towards purchase of certain brands of products. So, marketers try to create a unique position in the consumer's mind by developing their products into brand.

II. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Keller et al., "Impact of brand awareness and brand loyalty on consumer purchase decision", (2021), in this study the authors stated that there are many factors that influence the brand loyalty of the consumers. Consumers tend to remember famous brand names much better than the non-famous ones. Even though there are many alternative brands in the market, consumers have more faith and trust in famous brand names and these reputed brand names cause them to irrespective of the product price.

Awan Abdul Ghafoor et al., "Impact of brand loyalty on consumer buying behavior", (2019), the authors have mentioned in this paper consumer satisfaction and brand loyalty are two of the major marketing goals for most companies. Consumer loyalty is being considered to be a multidimensional phenomenon. The study took at the impact of customer satisfaction on brand loyalty for durable goods.

Suchmitt "A study on brand experience and brand loyalty" (2011), in his study the marketing practitioners have come to realize that understanding how consumers experience brands and in turn, how to provide appealing brand experience for them, is ensuring loyalty in a competitive market place. Thus, in today's competitive era, where companies are frantically searching for ways to ensure brand loyalty, delivering unique brand experiences might be a potential differentiation tool.

Jacoby et al., "A study on brand loyalty and customer loyalty", (2010), in this study authors defined brand loyalty as "the biased, behavioral response, expressed over time, by some decision-making unit with respect to one or more alternative brands out of a set of such brands, and is a function of psychological decision making, evaluative processes".

Richardson et al., "The impact of brand on consumer behavior" (1996), the authors have mentioned that purchasing experience is more in the older person than the younger one. The older people consider diversified opinion through the experience they have fact that the brand has an impact on consumer decision making process.

III. RESEARCH DESIGN

➤ *Objectives of the Study:*

- *To analyze the factors that affects the buying decision of consumers among the college students.*
- *To study the contribution of brand loyalty on consumer buying behavior among the college students.*

➤ *Statement of the Problem:*

Consumer behavior is the study of individuals, groups or organizations and all the activities associated with the purchase, use and disposal of branded products and services and it also included the emotions, attitudes and preferences of the consumers contribute towards brand loyalty to make buying decisions. Now a days there are many brands are emerging in the market and it has influence of certain factors which is affected to buy branded products among the college students so, it is important to know how the factors of consumer behavior impact on students buying decisions.

➤ *Sources of Data:*

This research is analytical in nature. The study is based on primary data collected from questionnaire.

➤ *Tools of Data Collection:*

The main purpose of this study is to research a tool for brand loyalty on consumer buying behavior by analyzing and reviewing of questionnaire among the college students.

➤ *Limitations of the Study:*

One of the main limitations of this study is that, it is an analytical paper and this study is limited to brand loyalty on consumer behavior among the college students. Besides that, the details study has been conducted taking primary data through questionnaire.

➤ *Consumer:*

A consumer is a person or an organizational unit that plays a role in the consumption of a transaction with the marketers or an entity.

• *The five Main buying Roles of Consumer:*

- ✓ **The initiator-** the person who decides to start the buying process.
- ✓ **The influencer-** the person who tries to convince others that they need the product.
- ✓ **The decider-** the person who makes the final decision to purchase.
- ✓ **The buyer-** the person who is going to pay.
- ✓ **The user-** the person who ends up using same branded product.

➤ *Consumer Buying behavior:*

Consumer buying behavior is the sum of a consumer’s attitudes, preferences, intentions, and decisions regarding the consumer’s behavior in the marketplace when purchasing a product or services. The study of consumer behavior answers the following questions about the consumers what they buy, when they buy it, how they buy it, where they buy it, and how often they buy it.

➤ *Brand Loyalty:*

Brand loyalty is when customers continue to purchase from the same brand over and over again, despite competitors offering similar products and services. Not only do customers continue engaging and purchasing from the same brand, but they also associate positive feeling towards that brand.

➤ *Data analysis and Interpretation:*

Data analysis and interpretation of questions are as follow:

- *Age Group of the Respondents*

Table 1 Age Group

Age Group		
Particulars	No. of Respondent	Percentage (%)
18-20	45	40
20-22	29	26
22-24	28	25
24-26	4	4
26-28	6	5
Total	112	100

Analysis: From the above table we can analyze that, 40% of respondents are under Age group of 18-20 and 4% of students are in the 24-26 age group.

Fig 1 Age Group

Interpretation: From the above graph we can interpret that most of the data is collected from undergraduate students at the age group of 18-20 and 4% of data is collected from the age group of 24-26.

- Are you a Loyal Customer for any Particular brand? If YES, which you like and use?

Table 2 Loyal Customer of any Particular Brand

Loyal customer of any particular brand		
Particulars	No. of Respondent	Percentage (%)
Yes	78	70
No	34	30
Total	112	100

Analysis: From the above table we can analyze that, 70% of students are loyal for their liked brands and only 30% of students are not using the branded products regularly in their buying decisions.

Fig 2 Percentage (%)

Interpretation: From the above table we can interpret that most of the students are using branded products and they are loyal to buy same products again and again responds from the students is that most of product which they like and use is Puma, Adidas, Lakme, Gucchi, Samsung, Colgate, LG and so on.

- *Does the Quality of Branded Products Influence you?*

Table 3 Influence of Quality on Branded Products

Influence of quality on branded products		
Particulars	No. of Respondent	Percentage (%)
Yes	85	75.89
No	5	4.46
May be	15	13.39
Sometimes	7	6.25
Total	112	100

Analysis: From the above table shows that 75.89% of respondents are influenced by quality of branded products and 4.46% of respondents are not getting any influence from quality.

Fig 3 Influence of Quality on Branded Products

Interpretation: From the above bar graph shows that influence of quality on branded products were, more no of students are trusting the quality of branded product which the company is offering.

- *Does the Price of Branded Product Influence you?*

Table 4 Influence of Quality on Branded Products

Influence of quality on branded products		
Particulars	No. of Respondent	Percentage (%)
Yes	66	59
No	9	8
May be	23	21
Sometimes	14	12
Total	112	100

Analysis: From the above table shows that 59% of respondents are influenced by price, 21% of respondents are may be influenced by price and 8% of respondents are not getting any influence from price.

Fig 4 Influence of Quality on Branded Products

Interpretation: From the above graph shows that influence of price on branded products. 59% of students are influenced by price and 21% of students are thinking price may influence when purchasing a branded products and according to 8% of respondents price is not influences when purchasing a branded product.

- Which of the following factors affect the buying decision for you?

Table 5 Factors Affecting for Buying Decision

Factors affecting for buying decision		
Particulars	No. of Respondent	Percentage (%)
Brand image	30	27
Promotion	9	8
Advertisement	19	17
Brand ambassadors	11	10
Price	43	38
Total	112	100

Analysis: From the above table shows that 38% of respondents are affected by price, 27% from the brand image, 17% from advertisement, 10% from brand ambassadors and 8% from promotion of the products.

Fig 5 Factors affect for Buying Decision

Interpretation: From the above pie chart shows that factors affecting when the students are going to make buying decisions of particular brand. Price, brand image and advertisement will affect more than the brand ambassador and promotion.

- *What are the Sources of Product Brand Information?*

Table 6 Sources of Product Brand Information

Sources of product brand information		
Particulars	No. of Respondent	Percentage (%)
Family	15	13
Peers	29	26
TV ads	38	34
Website	30	27
Total	112	100

Analysis: From the above table shows that 34% of students are receiving information about branded products through TV ads, 27% from website, 26% from peers and only 13% from family.

Fig 6 Sources of Product Brand Information

Interpretation: From the above graph shows that students are getting more information about branded products from TV ads, website and peers than the family.

- *The brand product you choose to buy meets your needs everytime?*

Table 7 Satisfaction of needs

Satisfaction of needs		
Particulars	No. of Respondent	Percentage (%)
Strongly agree	34	30
Agree	56	50
Neither agree not disagree	17	15
Disagree	4	4
Strongly disagree	1	1
Total	112	100

Analysis: From the above table shows that 50% of respondents are agree with satisfaction of branded product, 30% of strongly agree, only 4% and 1% of students are not agree with branded product to fulfill their purchasing needs.

Fig 7 Satisfaction of Needs

Interpretation: From the above graph we can interpret that most of the respondents are agree that the branded product will satisfy their need and only less percentage of respondents are disagreed for purchasing a branded product does not fulfill their needs.

- How likely are you to continue using branded products?

Table 8 Likeliness of Continuous Purchase of Branded Products

Likeliness of continuous purchase of branded products		
Particulars	No. of Respondent	Percentage (%)
Very likely	36	32
Likely	45	40
Neutral	21	19
Somewhat likely	9	8
Not likely	1	1
Total	112	100

Analysis: From the above table we can analyze that 40% of respondents are likely to purchase branded products continuously and 32% of respondents are very likely to purchase only 1% of respondent are not likely to purchase branded product continuously.

Fig 8 Likeliness of Continuous Purchase of Branded Products

Interpretation: From the above chart we can analyze that most of the people are very and likely to purchase branded product continuously and only less % of people are not using branded product everytime.

IV. FINDINGS

From the above research “A study on impact of brand loyalty on consumer buying behavior among the college students find that, 30% of respondents are not using and not loyal for any of the branded products. Price and quality will influence most for the buying decision. Price and brand image are more affecting factors for buying the branded products.

V. SUGGESTIONS

- Companies should understand the students needs and current trends and should provide good quality of product with reasonable price.
- Handle the customers complaints or product in a friendly manner.
- Perceived good product performance is a key driver of brand loyalty and also it influences customer satisfaction.

VI. CONCLUSION

Consumer behavior is the study of how consumers select and buy goods, services, ideas to satisfy their needs. If the company provides good quality of goods and services with reasonable price to the students, they may purchase more and loyal to the same brand. Brand loyalty has a great impact on consumer’s behavior. Once a brand maintains strong loyalty, marketing efforts will be reduced because loyal consumers will help to promote the brand positively.

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